

**STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN THE
CONSUMER ELECTRONICS INDUSTRY: THE ARZUM
CASE**

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I declare that all the information in this study, is collected and presented in accordance with academic rules and ethical principles, and that all information and documents that are not original in the study are referenced in accordance with the citation standards, within the framework required by the rules and principles.

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ABSTRACT

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M.A. in Business Administration

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Within the strategic management framework, companies should evaluate the conditions in their internal and external environment correctly when setting targets. Companies can use various strategic management tools to gain a competitive advantage. In this project, Arzum company, which is one of the market leaders of the small household appliances sector in Turkey, are examined. The competitive situation in the sector are determined by using the Five Forces Analysis, and the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the company will be determined through the SWOT analysis. After that, the strategic alternatives for the company are evaluated by matching the factors determined in the SWOT analysis in the SWOT matrix. Finally, whether the strategy determined using the space matrix is suitable for the company is analyzed.

Keywords: Arzum, strategic management, five forces analysis, swot analysis, swot matrix, space matrix, consumer electronics industry, small home appliances industry.

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ÖZET

TÜKETİCİ ELEKTRONİĞİ SEKTÖRÜNDE STRATEJİK YÖNETİM UYGULAMALARI: ARZUM ÖRNEĞİ

Osman BOZKURT

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Stratejik yönetim çerçevesinde şirketler hedeflerini belirlerken iç ve dış çevrelerindeki koşulları doğru değerlendirmek zorundadırlar. Şirketler rekabet avantajı elde etmek için çeşitli stratejik yönetim araçlarını kullanabilirler. Bu projede Türkiye'de küçük ev aletleri sektörünün pazar liderlerinden biri olan Arzum firması incelenmektedir. Beş Kuvvet Analizi kullanılarak sektördeki rekabet durumu belirlenirken, SWOT analizi ile şirketin güçlü ve zayıf yönleri, fırsat ve tehditleri belirlenecektir. Daha sonra SWOT analizinde belirlenen faktörler SWOT matrisinde eşleştirilerek şirket için stratejik alternatifler değerlendirilir. Son olarak uzay matrisi kullanılarak belirlenen stratejinin şirket için uygun olup olmadığı analiz edilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Arzum, stratejik yönetim, beş güç analizi, swot analizi, swot matrisi, space matrisi, tüketici elektroniği sektörü, küçük ev aletleri sektörü.

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INTRODUCTION

Companies are legal entities established to achieve a specific goal. They have to act by the legal and financial rules for which they are responsible. There may be various decisions that companies have taken to achieve their goals. For example, how to increase the number of customers, how the company will be positioned in the market, how to achieve financial performance targets, how to gain a competitive advantage against competitors, what opportunities will be used to grow the company, how to deal with economic and legal conditions that the company cannot control the position will be taken. The people who will implement these actions are the company managers, the sequence of activities to be carried out is called strategic management (Thompson et al., 2022).

Organizational success is also necessary for strategic management to be successful. It is imperative that all units in the organization act with the determined strategies. Firms can also distribute their resources in various geographical regions to gain a competitive advantage against their competitors, such as establishing a manufacturing facility in a different country. The survival of companies is directly related to the strategic decisions to be made (Thompson et al., 2022).

When we examine the literature, three conditions are generally emphasized for companies to be successful. It is to set goals that are appropriate and consistent with the position of the company in the market in which it operates, to use its strengths and weaknesses against opportunities and threats, and to highlight the competencies and strengths that will create a competitive advantage against its competitors. Porter defined the success of companies as using the competitive advantage they will gain against their biggest competitors in the world to achieve solid and sustainable financial performance (Porter, 1991).

Operational efficiency provides companies with cost and quality advantages to gain an edge over their competitors, but operational efficiency is not a strategy. In the 1980s, Japanese companies gained an advantage over their competitors in terms of operational efficiency. It was seen that there is a limit to increasing efficiency as the capabilities of competitors in the field of operational efficiency increase. When it comes to the point where it is not possible to increase operational efficiency,

profitability has decreased due to mutual price reductions with competitors (Porter, 1996). Porter defined strategy as "Strategy is creating fit among a company's activities" (Porter, What is strategy?, 1996, p. 74).

The generally accepted strategic management model is shown in Figure-1. The stages of the process are strategy formulation, implementation and evaluation. The first step of strategic management is to define the mission, vision and goals. The cycle is not static but dynamic, it is not done only in a certain time period, a change in any of the internal or external factors affecting the company requires a change in the process (David et al., 2020).

Figure 1: The strategic management process

Source: (David, 1989, p. 91)

1. CONSUMER ELECTRONICS SECTOR

Consumer electronics products are mainly used for entertainment, communication, and relaxation purposes. The main product types are televisions, game consoles, mobile phones, digital cameras, wearable devices, and portable computers. The most prominent feature that distinguishes this category from others is that the products have complex software. Products produced in small household appliances include kettles, food processors, food preparers, fans, personal care products, vacuum cleaners, and ovens.

The most important feature of the industry is that the prices tend to decrease constantly. The reason for this is the developments in electronic and semiconductor technology and Moore's law.

The total revenue of the sector was realized as 1.06 trillion dollars in 2022. It is observed that sales revenues have increased regularly except for 2022. Total revenues of the industry for the past years are shared in Figure 1-1.

Figure 1-1: Consumer electronics sector total revenues

Source: Statista (2023)

In the consumer electronics sector, the number of sales by category is shared in Table 1-1. The importance of mobile devices in our daily lives is also reflected in the sales figures in the table, and portable devices have a large share in total sales.

Table 1-1: Sales of consumer electronics by category

Year	Sales volume (Unit '000)				
	Computers and peripherals	In-Car entertainment	In-Home consumer electronics	Portable consumer electronics	Total
2017	382581,7	46636	328086,2	1946951,6	2704255,5
2018	368172,7	42282	329585,9	2223138,8	2963179,4
2019	357853,3	38770,4	326319,4	2268642,8	2991585,9
2020	394261,9	33755,7	322538,1	2237052	2987607,7
2021	398758,7	31050,1	304888,2	2318799,3	3053496,3
2022	390717	28742,9	288035,1	2335775,4	3043270,4

Source: Euromonitor International. (2022, July)

The big companies in the sector and their market shares are as in Table 1-2. It is seen that China-based companies have increased their market shares.

Table 1-2: Company shares of consumer electronics

Company Name	Retail volume %					
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Samsung Corp	16,1	14,5	14,1	14	14,1	14,1
Apple Inc	9,7	10,4	10,6	11,3	12,4	12,9
BBK Electronics Corp Ltd	7,2	7,1	7,3	7,9	9,7	10
Xiaomi Corp	3,7	4,9	5,9	6,8	7,5	7,5
Huawei Technologies Co Ltd	6,2	6,9	8,6	7,6	4	3,4
Lenovo Group Ltd	3,5	3,4	3,3	3,2	3,3	3,3
Sony Corp	2,4	3,1	2,8	2,6	2,5	2,4
Shenzhen Zhixin New Inf. Tech. Co Ltd	-	-	-	0,2	1,5	1,9
Amazon.com Inc	1,3	1,6	1,7	1,8	1,8	1,8
HP Inc	2	1,8	1,8	1,9	1,9	1,8
Alphabet Inc	0,3	0,6	0,9	1	1,6	1,7
LG Corp	3,9	3,3	2,8	2,6	2,2	1,7
TCL Corp	1,5	1,4	1,4	1,6	1,3	1,3
Transsion Holdings	1	1	1	1,3	1,3	1,2
Bose Corp	0,4	0,8	0,9	0,9	1	1
Nokia Corp	1,7	1,6	1,4	1,4	1,1	1
Dell Technologies Inc	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,9	0,9
AsusTek Computer Inc	1,2	1	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8
Hisense Group	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,7	0,6	0,6
Acer Inc	0,8	0,7	0,6	0,6	0,6	0,6

Source: Euromonitor International. (2022, July).

The small household appliances sector is under the consumer electronics sector. Total worldwide sales revenue in 2019 was \$435.4 billion. Four-year sales revenue is shown in Figure 1-2.

Figure 1-2: Household appliances retail sales value

Source: Statista (2021)

According to Euromonitor statistics, the total sales of small household appliances in the world are as in Table 1-3. Starting from 2017 to 2021, sales traditions have increased. The sales custom decreased in 2022 compared to the previous year.

Table 1-3: Global small home appliance sales quantities

Year	Unit ('000)	% Growth YoY
2017	2.346.314	-
2018	2.431.271	3,49%
2019	2.508.991	3,10%
2020	2.528.075	0,75%
2021	2.533.794	0,23%
2022	2.524.319	-0,38%

Source: Euromonitor International. (2023, April)

The leading large companies operating in the small household appliances sector and their market shares are given in Table 1-4. The market share of Arzum, which we will examine in the study, is also shown.

Table 1-4: Global small household application sector market share

Company name	Market share					
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Midea Group Co Ltd	5,4	5,5	5,7	5,6	5,4	5,5
SEB Groupe	4,4	4,4	4,5	4,4	4,4	4,4
Spectrum Brands Holdings Inc	3,4	3,3	3,2	3,3	3,3	3,3
Procter & Gamble Co	3,4	3,3	3,3	3,3	3,3	3,3
Koninklijke Philips NV	5,9	5,8	5,8	5,6	3	3
Conair Corp	2,7	2,7	2,6	2,7	2,7	2,8
Newell Brands Inc	2,9	2,8	2,7	2,7	2,7	2,7
Panasonic Corp	2,5	2,5	2,4	2,3	2,3	2,2
Philips Domestic Appliance	-	-	-	-	2,2	2,1
Shanghai Flyco Electrical Appliance Co Ltd	2,3	2,2	2	1,9	1,8	1,9
Zhuhai Gree Group Co Ltd	2	1,9	1,8	1,6	1,7	1,8
Joyoung Co Ltd	1,7	1,6	1,7	1,7	1,6	1,6
De'Longhi SpA	1,4	1,4	1,4	1,4	1,6	1,6
Hamilton Beach Brands Holding Co	1,5	1,5	1,4	1,5	1,5	1,5
Haier Group	0,8	0,9	0,9	1	1,1	1,1
Xiaomi Corp	0,1	0,3	0,4	0,6	0,9	1
BSH Hausgeräte GmbH	1,1	1	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,9
Britânia Eletrodomésticos SA	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,8	0,8
Dyson Ltd	0,5	0,6	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,7
Arzum Elektrikli Ev Aletleri San ve Tic AS	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1
Others	57,2	57,5	57,8	58	58	57,7
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Euromonitor International. (2023, April).

According to the Annual Report of the Council of Durable Consumer Goods (The Union of Chambers and Commodity Exchanges of Turkey, TOBB, 2020), small household appliances produced in Turkey include food processors, water heaters, food preparers, vacuum cleaners, hair dryers, irons, electric heaters, ovens, consists of electric cookers, fans and personal care appliances. Vacuum cleaners account for 40% of the total market share, while irons account for 15%. The contribution of the sector to employment is twenty thousand people.

Annual sales quantities and annual changes in the Turkish market are shown in Table 1-5. When we compare the year 2022 with the previous year, it shows a stable outlook.

Table 1-5: Turkey's small home appliances market sales quantities

Year	Market size (Unit)	% Growth YoY
2017	30.322.900	
2018	27.520.900	-9,24%
2019	26.119.100	-5,09%
2020	27.245.600	4,31%
2021	28.405.400	4,26%
2022	28.390.200	-0,05%

Source: Euromonitor International. (2022, December)

For small household appliances, 40% of Türkiye's sector turnover is realized in the Marmara region, and 30% of sales are made through dealers. (TOBB, 2020).

The total sales revenue generated in the small household appliances sector in Turkey is shown in Figure 1-3. The revenue obtained in 2022 decreased compared to the previous year.

Figure 1-3: Sales revenue of small household appliances sold in Turkey

Source: Statista (2023/1)

The market shares of the companies in the Turkish small household appliances market are as in Table 1-6. Arçelik is the market leader and Arzum is the second.

Table 1-6: Market shares of companies in the Turkish small household appliances market

Brand Name	Company Name	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Arçelik	Arçelik AS	14,2	13,4	13,9	14,3	14,5	14,6
Arzum	Arzum Elk. Ev Alt. San ve Tic A.Ş.	9,9	10,9	11,1	11,3	11,1	11,2
Fakir	Fakir-Hausgeräte GmbH	6,7	6,9	7	6,9	7	7,1
Philips (Phi. Dm. App.)	Philips Domestic Appliance	-	-	-	-	5,9	6,2
Tefal	SEB Groupe	5,8	5,8	5,1	4,5	4,2	4,6
Ufo	NNR Ltd Sti	3,3	3,2	3,4	3,6	3,5	3,3
Bosch	BSH Hausgeräte GmbH	3,8	3,4	3,2	3,3	3,4	3,2
Braun	Procter & Gamble Co	5,2	5,1	5,1	3,5	3,2	3,1
Sinbo	Depa Elektronik San ve Tic Ltd	3,6	3,2	3,1	3,2	3,1	3,1
Philips	Koninklijke Philips NV	9,1	9,1	9,5	9,1	3,1	3
Fantom	Fanset Elk. Ev Alt. San ve Tic Ltd Sti	2,6	2,6	2,4	2,5	2,3	2,5
Arnica	Senur Elektrik Motorlari San ve Tic AS	1,8	1,7	1,7	1,8	1,8	1,9
Kumtel	Kumtel Day. Tuk. Mal. San. Tic A.Ş.	1,7	1,7	1,8	2	1,9	1,8
Vestel	Zorlu Holding A.Ş	2	1,7	1,5	1,5	1,7	1,7
Korkmaz	Korkmaz Mutfak Eşyaları San Tic A.Ş.	0,7	1,2	1,2	1,3	1,2	1,2
Moser	Wahl Clipper Corp	0,1	0,2	0,2	1,1	1,1	1,1
Braun	De'Longhi SpA	1,6	1,5	1,2	1,2	1,1	1,1
Babyliss	Conair Corp	1	1	1	1	1	1
Samsung	Samsung Corp	0,7	0,8	0,7	0,7	0,9	0,9
Others	Others	26,2	26,6	26,9	27,2	28	27,4
	Total	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Euromonitor International. (2022, December)

2. INFORMATION ABOUT ARZUM

Arzum is a brand that was founded in the early 1950s and registered the brand "Arzum" in 1966 and started its activities in the small household appliances market. Its field of activity is to trade electrical household appliances through wholesalers, retailers, chain stores, and e-commerce. It is the brand that attaches the most importance to innovation and design among its competitors and has 650 products in its portfolio. Thanks to the company's emphasis on design and innovation, its products have received multiple awards. In the plus x award competition held in 2021, it won four awards, one from the IF Design design category and six awards from Haus&Garten's Sher Gut award. The 2022 targets are stable and sustainable growth, increasing the share in online marketplaces, product development for export markets, and more effective use of innovation and design.

The primary mission of Arzum's company is to make life easier by producing innovative, technological, well-designed products and services for every household and to be a brand that establishes a warm relationship with its stakeholders. Its vision is to be the brand that creates the most value for all its stakeholders.

The company decided to go public at the end of 2020, 47.5% of the partnership shares under the control of SDA International SARL were offered to the public in the range of 15.50-17 TL per share, and revenue of 260.000.000 TL was obtained from this. At the end of 2021, the equity distribution is as in Table 2-1, and the free float ratio is 49%.

Table 2-1: Shareholding of company partners

Shareholder	Share ratio %
Talip Murat Kolbaşı	10,71
Ali Osman Kolbaşı	9,52
Yasemin Rezan Kolbaşı	8,42
Zeynep Figen Peker	8,42
Aliye Kolbaşı	6,12
Rengin Yağan	3,91
Filiz Kolbaşı	0,98
Bora Kolbaşı	0,98
İbrahim Buğra kolbaşı	0,98

Kayra Kolbaşı	0,98
Public Stock	49

Source: (Arzum, 2023)

Arzum's senior management is shown in Figure 2-1, the board of directors consists of a chairman, a vice chairman, and four members.

Figure 2-1: The structure of Arzum's board of directors

Source: (Arzum, 2023)

The organizational structure is as in Figure 2-2 and exists in a hierarchical structure from top to bottom. Having the CEO on the board of directors helps ensure a healthy flow of information from the board to the company.

Arzum follows a human resources policy in line with company values, mission, and vision. These policies consist of the acquisition and retention of talented people, the implementation of new working models, the creation of a high-performance culture, the incorporation of digitalization into the company culture, the increase of productivity, and preferred employer focal points.

Figure 2-2: Arzum department structure and managers

Source: (Arzum, 2023)

The company prepares individual development plans for the talent management and development of its employees; each employee is evaluated according to their competence and is encouraged to receive or give feedback on this. One focal point of the human resources strategy is that all employees have high performance, therefore, working environments that support innovative thinking and creativity are created. Every year, starting from the chief executive officer, all employees go through performance evaluation processes. Individual development plans and wage increase rates are determined by using performance evaluation reports. The company wants the candidate evaluated while hiring to be in line with Arzum's values. It pays attention that the competencies and abilities of the person to be recruited are suitable for the position; the Buddy program is applied in order to facilitate the orientation of the newly recruited employees. Arzum offices are designed entirely using glass so that employees in every position can be easily reached. It helps to convey the needs of the employee in any position to the management through an online program called "We Have a Desire". Arzum sets a policy to create occupational health and safety awareness in all its employees, and accordingly, occupational health and safety training is repeated at regular intervals. In this training, in addition to the measures for the physical health of the employee, their mental and mental health is also supported. In order to increase the loyalty of the employees to the company, seniority awards are organized for each 5-year working period. In determining the wages of the employees, support is received from independent and international consultant companies. There is

no discrimination based on language, religion, race, or gender in the determination of wages.

As of the end of 2022, the rate of female employees in the company is 45%, 69% of the company employees are Y generation, and the total number of employees is 170. Arzum Turkey's women's chess championship sponsorship has continued uninterrupted for 15 years. It has sponsored Galatasaray Hepsiburada women's football club in order to support the idea that women are there in every field.

Arzum's sales and profitability tend to increase over the years. Sales increased in 2022 compared to 2021, but net income decreased due to the increase in interest expenses incurred in 2022. The detailed income statement for the last four years is shown in Table 2-2.

Table 2-2: Arzum's income statement (2022-2021-2020-2019)

INCOME STATEMENT				
The fiscal year is January-December. All values TRY millions	2019	2020	2021	2022
Sales/Revenue	448	607	815	1,538
Cost of Goods Sold (COGS) incl. D&A	315	421	561	1,057
Gross Income	133	187	255	481
SG&A Expense	91	134	175	325
Other Operating Expense	1	-2	-1	-9
EBIT	42	55	80	147
Unusual Expense	2	-3	-	-
Non-Operating Income/Expenses	4	2	21	21
Non-Operating Interest Income	1	1	1	11
Interest Expense	23	13	40	125
Pretax Income	21	48	62	55
Income Tax	5	12	12	14
Consolidated Net Income	15	36	50	41
Net Income	15	36	50	41

Source: The Wall Street Journal (2023)

The balance sheet information of Arzum's for the last four years is as in table 2-3. The size of the company's balance sheet has been increasing over the years. In

2022, short-term borrowings increased 2.5 times compared to the previous year. This is the reason for the increase in interest expenses.

Table 2-3: Arzum's balance sheet (2022-2021-2020-2019)

BALANCE SHEET				
The fiscal year is January-December. All values TRY millions	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total Assets	318,16	531,18	743,95	1.325,88
Total Current Assets	288,86	477,69	666,82	1.208,24
Cash, Cash Equivalents, and Short Term Investments	8,2	29,74	94,54	316,31
Inventories	45,78	134,71	216,5	240,93
Trade and Other Receivables, Current	225,52	304,81	324,08	609,58
Prepayments and Deposits, Current	9,36	8,43	31,28	41,08
Other Current Assets	0		0,41	0,34
Derivative Investment and Hedging Assets, Current	0			
Total Non-Current Assets	29,3	53,49	77,13	117,64
Net Property, Plant, and Equipment	22,13	35,95	48,21	62,06
Investment Properties and Properties Held for Development	0,48	0,15	0,15	0,14
Net Intangible Assets	3,6	4,93	9,22	13,64
Trade and Other Receivables, Non-Current	0	2,17	3,8	5,97
Prepayments and Deposits, Non-Current	0,53	0,47	0,31	2,06
Deferred Tax Assets, Non-Current	2,56	9,82	15,44	33,77
Total Liabilities	219,44	399,4	568,32	1.123,88
Total Current Liabilities	213,05	388,34	537,39	1.108,84
Payables and Accrued Expenses, Current	120,51	223,14	231,46	356,7
Financial Liabilities, Current	65,89	116,31	252,56	636,61
Provisions, Current	6,29	14,77	13,86	29,31
Deferred Liabilities, Current	18,91	34,09	39,51	86,07
Other Current Liabilities	1,45	0,02		0,14
Total Non-Current Liabilities	6,39	11,06	30,92	15,05
Financial Liabilities, Non-Current	1,89	4,22	23,93	0,85
Provisions, Non-Current	4,5	6,84	7	14,2
Total Equity	98,72	131,78	175,63	201,99
Equity Attributable to Parent Stockholders	98,72	131,78	175,63	201,99
Paid in Capital	50,85	50,85	50,85	50,85
Retained Earnings/Accumulated Deficit	43,37	74,95	110,91	135,2

Reserves/Accumulated/Comprehensive Income/Losses	4,36	5,83	13,73	15,8
Other Equity Interest	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15

Source: Morningstar (2023)

Arzum does not own any production facility in or out of Türkiye. 80% of the product supply is from suppliers in Turkey, and the remaining part is from foreign suppliers.

As can be seen in Figure 2-3, while the share of traditional channels in sales channels has decreased over the years, the share of modern sales channels is increasing.

Figure 2-3: Distribution of Arzum sales channels

Source: Arzum (2023)

Arzum products are sold in 48 countries around the world. Although total sales are on an increasing trend in Figure 2-4, the share of exports in total sales decreased in 2022.

Figure 2-4: Distribution of Arzum's total sales by market

Source: Arzum (2023)

Distribution of sales by geographical regions is shown in Table 2-4, and the most important export markets are Egypt, Germany, and Kuwait.

Table 2-4: Distribution of total sales by country

Revenues	2021	2022
Turkey	710.643.568	1.370.114.253
Egypt	28.272.012	8.830.435
Germany	16.080.256	15.346.442
Kuwait	9.574.267	10.416.144
Other countries	50.775.856	133.198.594
Net Revenue	815.345.959	1.537.905.868

Source: Arzum (2023)

Arzum has strong competitors in the local and global markets. In the global market in 2022, Midea Group Co Ltd is the strongest competitor with a 5.5% market share (Table 2-2), and Arçelik is the strongest competitor with a 14.6% market share in the local market (Table 2-4).

2.1 The differentiated Arzum products

Arzum is a company with a history of 55 years operating in the small household appliances sector, with 650 different products in its product portfolio. Various features distinguish arzum from other manufacturers; they attach great importance to innovation to become a well-known brand at the global level. Apart from the domestic market, they export to more than 60 countries and differentiate their products according to the countries they export to increase their sales abroad. To make global sales more effective, the company has switched to a regional-based management system. Accordingly Arzum Europe GmbH was established for the European market, and a director-level appointment was made. They are planning to open representative offices in different regions in line with this policy for the future.

The Covid-19 pandemic has caused many of us to change our diet and habits. As a result of the breaks, uncertainties, and restrictions in the global supply chain, there were significant decreases in trade volumes. To turn this situation into a competitive

advantage, Arzum used its mobile application and direct product delivery efforts, starting with the slogan "Arzum is on the way". As a result of the increasing demand for healthy nutrition, product development activities for healthy food have been accelerated.

The importance given to innovation and efficiency has brought Arzum various awards in the international arena. In the Plus X Award competition held in 2021, they received 11 awards for their four products. Arzum Okka Minio Jet was deemed worthy of the year's best award. Arzum Maxi Grill Pro Multi-functional cooker, Arzum clean force vacuum cleaner, and Arzum toaster are other products that received awards. They were selected as the brand of the year in the electrical household appliances category in the A.L.F.A awards. Haus & Garten Arzum, the consumer products testing magazine published in Germany, gave OKKA Grandio an excellent grade of 1.3, the highest quality ever received in this category.

Arzum was added to the women-friendly companies stock index by İř portfolio management company and KOÇ-KAM. The rate of female employees on the board of directors is 33%, and the rate of female employees in the company is 40%.

3. PORTER'S FIVE FORCES ANALYSIS

3.1 Five forces analysis definition

The first source we came across with the five forces analysis is the March-April 1979 issue of harvard business review¹. In the article How Competitive Forces Shape Strategy published by Michael E. Porter, he talked about the details of the five forces analysis.

A company's core strategy is to maintain its business and cope with the competition in the market. When we say competition, we only think of our competitors from a narrow perspective. While this is true, there are forces outside of our competitors that affect our company—buyers, suppliers, new competitors, and substitutes. If we examine the sector we are in terms of these five forces while creating a strategy, we can better understand the competitive structure of the sector and gain a stronger position against our competitors. (Porter, 1979). The forces governing competition in an industry are as in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1: Forces governing competition in an industry

Source: (Porter, 1979, p. 141)

¹ <https://hbr.org/1979/03/how-competitive-forces-shape-strategy>

Each of the five forces is analyzed during the analysis phase. The first of these, the threat of entry, expresses the difficulties faced by new competitors entering the industry and the extent of the threat that their entry into the industry will pose to us. From our point of view, the entry threat of a new company entering the market is high. In an industry with a high entry threat, profitability must be limited, and investments must be made to deter potential competitors (Porter, 1979).

Another factor affecting our competitiveness is the power of suppliers, the strength of the suppliers in the industry reduces competitiveness. For example, if the number of suppliers you can supply the inputs used in your activities is one and there is no alternative, price increases by your supplier will increase your costs, decrease your profitability, and cause some of the profit you will gain to shift to the supplier and ultimately affect your competitiveness negatively. There are various ways to prevent this, you can diversify your suppliers, you can make various long-term price agreements with your suppliers to gain competitive advantage, or if you have a critical input in the industry, you can invest and produce it yourself to obtain it with your own means (Porter, 1979).

The power of buyers is another factor that affects the competitiveness of an industry. The fact that buyers prefer your competitors to gain a price advantage means that this power is high. Various strategies such as product differentiation, customer loyalty programs, purchasing incentives, or building high brand power can be applied to reduce the power of buyers (Porter, 1979).

The threat of substitutes is among the factors that affect our competitiveness. If there is a substitute product that can be used instead of the product that is the industry's output, this means that the threat of substitution is high and may reduce the industry's profit potential (Porter, 1979).

Competition among existing competitors has a negative impact on the profitability of the company. The factors affecting the intensity of competition in the sector are the high number of competitors and similar sizes, the low growth rate of the sector, high exit barriers, the presence of other state-supported competitors in the sector, and the fact that competitors do not know each other well (Porter, 1979).

3.2 Application of the model to the Arzum industry

If we interpret the competitive environment in the small household appliances sector within the framework of five forces: Threat of entry into the industry does not require a lot of know-how, and there is no legal barrier, so the threat of new entrants is high. The power of suppliers is low because the inputs we use in production are of the type that can be produced without having too much technical knowledge. There are sufficient suppliers both at home and abroad. The power of buyers is high because we have so many competitors in the industry, the buyers can easily choose the brand that is advantageous for them when making a purchasing decision. The threat of substitutes is low because there are no other substitutes for the products produced in this industry. Rivalry among existing competitors is high, and there is a large number of competitors. As a result of the evaluations, the competitive situation of the industry is as in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1: Small home appliances industry five forces analysis application

Low-intensity forces	High-intensity forces
The power of suppliers	Threat of entry
The threat of substitutes	The power of buyers
	Rivalry among existing competitors

4. SWOT ANALYSIS

4.1 SWOT table definition, advantages and disadvantages

It is accepted that SWOT analysis has its origins in Albert Humphrey, a Stanford University professor who led a research project on Fortune 500 companies in the USA in the 1960s and 1970s, but there is no academic reference to support it (Helms & Nixon, 2010)

If we look at how the SWOT analysis is prepared in a 2x2 matrix, there are strengths and weaknesses at the top, opportunities and threats at the bottom, respectively. The upper part of the matrix is related to the internal factors of the company, and the lower part is related to the external factors, it is known as the most frequently used strategic planning technique thanks to its simple and understandable structure. (Helms & Nixon, 2010). An exemplary SWOT analysis application is shared in Table 4-1.

Companies must compete with their competitors to survive and be successful. The main purpose of the competition is that the company has sustainable and stronger financial opportunities against its competitors. SWOT analysis helps companies at the stage of how to construct the strategies to be followed. Since the factors affecting the company can change over time, the SWOT table prepared should be in a dynamic structure and should be revised according to the changing factors (Porter, 1991).

SWOT analysis can be prepared by the managers within the company or with the support of a consultant firm outside the company. In outsourcing, it is necessary to get help from the managers and employees within the company to get to know the company closely, this will also inform the consultant company about the competence of the managers and employees in the company. The factors to be added to the matrix are very important, scoring according to the degree of importance after the factors are determined is a frequently used technique, adding the high-scoring factors to the SWOT and eliminating the low-scoring factors will ensure that the prepared analysis is close to perfect (Pickton & Wright, 1998).

4.2 Arzum SWOT analysis

While preparing the SWOT matrix of my desire, the information shared in the previous parts of the study was used. The SWOT analysis prepared is as in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1: Arzum's SWOT analysis

<p>Strengths</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1) Strong in the domestic market.2) High brand awareness.3) Importance is given to R&D and design.4) Increase in sales in modern channels.5) Making special product differentiation for export markets.	<p>Weakness</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1) No own production facility.2) Overdependence on suppliers.3) Low global market share.4) Decreasing the share of exports in total sales.5) Decrease in net income.6) Weak global presence.
<p>Opportunities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1) Enter new foreign markets.2) Enter the category of smart small home appliances.3) Increasing online shopping in the world.4) Focus on sustainability.5) The government's efforts to protect the domestic producer.	<p>Threats</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1) Recession expectation in the global economy.2) Instability in the Turkish economy.3) Increase in raw material costs due to inflation.4) High competition in the small house appliances market.5) Disruptions caused by Covid-19 in the supply chain.

5. SWOT MATRIX

5.1 SWOT matrix definition

The name of the SWOT matrix is also referred to as the TOWS matrix in some sources, although their names seem different, they represent the same thing. The purpose of the TOWS matrix is to match external threats and opportunities with the company's internal weaknesses and strengths and determine a strategy. There are three different approaches when analyzing the table situation, identifying important problems, setting goals and objectives, and focusing on opportunities. While performing the analysis, a strategy can be created by using the external environment, internal environment, or both factors at the same time (Wehrich, 1982).

Using the TOWS matrix, it is possible to strategize in four different ways as WT, WO, ST, SO. The aim of WT strategy is to reduce weaknesses and threats, WO strategy is to reduce weaknesses and take advantage of opportunities, ST strategy is to use strengths and deal with threats, and SO strategy is to use strengths and opportunities to gain a better position (Wehrich, 1982). The structure of the TOWS matrix is as in Table 5-1.

Table 5-1: An example TOWS matrix structure

TOWS analysis	List internal strengths (S)	List internal weaknesses (W)
List external opportunities (O)	SO(maxi-maxi)	ST(maxi-mini)
List external threats (T)	WO (mini-maxi)	WT (mini-mini)

Source: (Wehrich, 1982, p. 10)

5.2 Arzum SWOT matrix

In Table 5-2, we write the factors included in the SWOT analysis we created for Arzum in the relevant fields in the TOWS analysis table. When we matched WT, WO, ST, SO, we got eight different strategies.

Table 5-2: Arzum's SWOT matrix

<p>SWOT analysis</p>	<p>List Internal Strengths (S)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Strong in the domestic market. 2) High brand awareness. 3) Importance is given to R&D and design. 4) Increase in sales in modern channels. 5) Making special product differentiation for export markets. 	<p>List Internal Weaknesses (W)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No own production facility. 2) Overdependence on suppliers. 3) Low global market share. 4) Decreasing the share of exports in total sales. 5) Decrease in net income. 6) Weak global presence.
<p>List External Opportunities (O)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Enter new foreign markets 2) Enter the category of smart small home appliances. 3) Increasing online shopping in the world. 4) Focus on sustainability. 5) The government's efforts to protect the domestic producer. 	<p>SO (maxi-maxi)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) S3O2 Developing a new product in the smart device category by using its strength in R&D and design. 2) S1O5 Taking market share from imported competitors by using strong position and incentives in the market 	<p>WO (mini-maxi)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) W6O1 Increasing its global awareness by being present in other countries. 2) W3O3 To increase the global market share by using direct online sales channels. 3) W2O4 Establishing a production facility that adheres to sustainability principles to reduce dependency on suppliers
<p>List External Threats (T)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Recession expectation in the global economy. 2) Instability in the Turkish economy. 3) Increase in raw material costs due to inflation. 4) High competition in the small house appliances market. 5) Disruptions caused by Covid-19 in the supply chain. 	<p>ST (maxi-mini)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) S5T2 To increase foreign exchange revenues by offering more differentiated products to foreign markets in order not to be affected by the instability in the Turkish economy. 2) S2T4 Turning high brand awareness into competitive advantage. 	<p>WT (mini-mini)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) W1T5 To avoid disruptions in the supply chain by establishing a production facility.

6. SPACE MATRIX

6.1 SPACE matrix definition

The Strategic Positioning and Action Evaluation (SPACE) matrix is a tool used by a company to determine the right strategies or to reveal whether the identified strategies are appropriate. The matrix has the x and y axes intersecting each other perpendicularly, the two inner dimensions of the axes represent the financial position (FP) and the competitive position (CP), while the two outer dimensions represent the stability position (SP) and the industry position (IP). While preparing the matrix, factors should be determined and scored for each dimension, and the score should be divided by the total number of factors. For the factors to be selected, the IFE EFE matrix can be used, as well as different factors depending on the structure of the industry. The scores of FP and SP on the same axis are summed, and their location is marked on the x-axis, in the same way, the location is marked in the CP and IP on the y-axis, and then the location of the vector is formed by the line drawn from the origin of the space matrix to the intersection point of the (x,y) coordinate. The strategy that the company should prioritize emerges (David et al., 2020). Figure 6-1 shows the structure of the SPACE matrix.

6.2 Arzum SPACE matrix

The factor scoring, which is the first step of creating a SPACE matrix, was made in Table 6-1. As a result of the scoring, 1.2 points on the y-axis and 1.6 points on the x-axis were obtained

The line drawn from the origin of the matrix (x,y) to the intersection point is formed in the aggressive region in Figure 6-2. A company with an aggressive position should focus on the strategies identified in Figure 6-1.

Figure 6-1: SPACE matrix structure

Source: (David et al., 2020, p. 170)

Table 6-1: Space matrix x and y axis scoring table

Internal analysis (-7 worst, -1 good)		External analysis (+1 worst, +7 good)	
Competitive position (CP)-		Industry position (IP)+	
Market share	-3	Growth potential	4
Product quality	-2	Financial stability	4
Technological know-how	-3	Ease of entry into market	4
Product variety	-2	Profit Potential	3
Use of technology	-3	Alternative products	4
Competitive Position (CP) Average	-2,6	Industry Position (IP) Average	+3.8
Total axis Y score 1.2			
Internal analysis (+1 worst, +7 good)		External analysis (-7 worst, -1 good)	
Financial position (FP) +		Stability position (SP)-	
Enterprise value	4	Competitive pressure	-2
Liquidity	5	Price comparison	-2

Working capital	6	Demand variability	-2
EPS	5	Barriers to entry into market	-4
Cash flows	4	Rate of inflation	-6
Financial Position (FP) Average	4,8	Stability Position (SP) Average	-3,2
Total axis X score 1,6			

Figure 6-2: Arzum's SPACE matrix profiles

CONCLUSION

Strategic management is a requirement for companies to take positions in line with changing internal and external conditions. Companies that do not attach importance to strategy formulation and implementation processes cannot gain or maintain competitive advantage. For example, Nokia was the leader of the mobile phone industry with a 53% market share in the mobile phone market in 2013. Arzum's competitors in the small household appliances sector, in which it operates, are quite strong and the majority of them produce products in different categories. The intense competition in the sector is always a pressure factor on companies. Strategies to be chosen in sectors where competition is intense should exhibit an aggressive profile. Arzum is successful in product development and product differentiation and this strategy is a suitable strategy to gain competitive advantage against its competitors. The fact that Arzum does not have any production facility means that it is excessively dependent on the suppliers, and the W1T5 strategy determined in the SWOT matrix related to this will reduce the dependence on the suppliers and the situation of disruption in the supply chain may cease to be a threat for Arzum. It can be solved by establishing a production facility or by purchasing a supplier who owns this facility. The purchase of the supplier is horizontal integration and conforms to the aggressive position profile determined in the SPACE matrix.

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